

Migration Trends in four metropolitan cities of India

Dr. Mahananda Kanjilal

Associate Professor, JCC College, Kolkata,
Guest Faculty, University of Calcutta, IGNOU, Vidyasagar University,
Resource person and Coordinator of SWAYAM of UGC

Abstract: As per Census of India, migration is movement of persons from place of birth. The reasons of migration may be economic, social and political. The present paper tries to examine pattern and trend of male migration of four mega cities of India namely Mumbai, Delhi, Kolkata and Chennai. Since urbanization is a major cause of migration the present paper also analyses migration due to urbanization. The paper takes into account the percentage of male migrants in India taking into account the census data for 1991, 2001 and 2011. The main reason for migration in all the metro cities was work followed by business and education. Mumbai had the largest number of migrants for work followed by Delhi, Kolkata and Chennai. Migrants from better off sections migrate for better job opportunities and for better higher education. Whereas migration of poor migrants take place to improve economic condition and reduction of poverty. According to 2011 census, Uttar Pradesh and Bihar have large number of out migrants. The number of interstate migrants grew at 55% between 1991 and 2001. This came to 33% between 2001 and 2011.

Keywords: migration, urbanization, metropolitan cities, census

Introduction

Migration refers to the movement of persons from the place of origin to another destination. Migrants by place of birth are those who are enumerated at a village or town at the time of census other than their place of birth. Migration or human mobility is governed by a set of social, economic, political, cultural and personal factors. Migration also takes place in search of improved livelihoods in terms of employment, education and other facilities. Migration is an intrinsic part of development. However economic factors dominate in comparison to other factors. Urbanization is increase in urban population. India's urban population is expected to grow from 377 million in 2011 to about 600 million for 2031. About 60% of the growth in urban population in the past is due to natural increase whereas migration has contributed to 20% of increase in urban population. There is a concentration of urban population in large cities and existing urban agglomeration. Past studies have shown that urbanization results in movement of people from rural to urban areas. Interstate inequality in terms of income per capita is still high in India which is a driving force behind interstate migration. More the inequality between rural and urban areas, higher is the migration

Objective and methodology

The present paper tries to understand the pattern and trend of male migration of four mega cities of India namely Mumbai, Delhi, Kolkata and Chennai. The secondary data from Census of 1991, 2001 and 2011 are used for the study. The paper also tries to relate urbanization with migration.

Analysis at the national level

Comparing 1991 census data with 2001 data for the country as a whole, it comes out that total migration was 307.1 million in 2001 in comparison to 229.8 million in 1991. The proportion of interstate migration has remained low over the decades since 1961. It was 3.4% in 1971 which declined to 3.2% in 1991.

Table 1: Internal migrants in population census (1960-2001)

Year	Percentage of migrants to total population
1961	30.8
1971	28.7
1981	29.4
1991	26.6
2001	29.3

Source: Census of India

Table I shows the percentage of migrants in total population for the country as a whole. It comes out that on an average 28.9 % are migrant population of the country.

Table 2: Reasons for migration in India in 2001(0 to 9 years)

Reasons	Persons as a % of total migrants	Persons as a % of total migrants	Male migrants as a % of total migrants	Male migrants as a % of total migrants
	1991	2001	1991	2001
Work/Employment	12.1	14.7	30.4	37.6
Business	2.7	1.2	6.6	2.9
Education	4.2	3	9	6.2
Marriage	44.9	43.8	2.6	2.1

Source: Census of India

From table 2 it comes out that marriage was the main reason behind migration in India. The percentage is high for females. In 2001, out of 65.4 million female migrants, 42.4 million women migrate for marriage. Among males, the main reason for migration was work or employment. 12.3 million out of 32.8 million males migrate for work or employment.

According to 2001 census, Maharashtra received largest number of migrants (7.9 million) followed by Delhi (5.6 million) and West Bengal (5.5 million). In 1991, the migrants of Maharashtra, Delhi and West Bengal were 4.3 million, 3.7 million and 5.1 million respectively. The data reflects sharp increase in migration in these states. In migration in last ten years is the largest in Greater Mumbai UA followed by Delhi. Proportion of migrants to total population was the largest in Delhi UA ((16.4%) followed by Greater Mumbai (15.1%).

Migration in four metropolitan cities of India

In 1951 there were only four metropolitan cities in India but in 2001 the number has increased to 35, a seven fold increase in 50 years. Delhi, Kolkata, Mumbai and Chennai are the leading metros in India. These cities have attracted migrants from all over the country.

Table 3: % of males in total migrants

Cities	Total	1991	%of Males	Total	2001	% of Males
		Male			Male	
Delhi	3290708	1801830	54.76	5550323	3111671	56.06
Mumbai	4436167	2494516	56.23	7141583	4137467	57.93
Calcutta	2617626	1381157	52.76	3735752	1994693	53.39
Chennai	1498195	769969	51.39	1608299	855103	53.17

Source: Census of India

It has been found that percentage of males in total migrants were more than 50% in both the years 1991 and 2001 in the metro cities taken under consideration.

This is shown in table 3.

Table 4: % of male migrants in total population

Cities	1991	2001	1991	2001
	Total Migrants		Male migrants	
Delhi	39.09	43.39	39.16	44.31
Mumbai	35.22	43.63	36.20	46.08
Calcutta	23.75	28.27	22.93	28.21
Chennai	27.63	25.03	27.44	25.96

Source: Census of India

In 1991 and 2001 total migrants and male migrants both increased in the four metro cities except in Chennai. This is alarming for the metro cities which are becoming overburdened with the problems of housing and provisioning of basic amenities. Increased urbanization is creating many socioeconomic problems in mega cities and increased migration is aggravating these problems.

Table 5: Percentage increase in population and male migration between 1991 and 2001

Cities	% increase in urban Population	% increase in male migration
Delhi	37.68	72.69
Mumbai	29.95	65.86
Kolkata	19.91	44.42
Chennai	18.50	11.05

Source: Census of India

Taking into account the percentage increase in population and percentage increase in male migration it comes out that in both the cases Delhi is the top position followed by Mumbai, Kolkata and Chennai. Percentage increase in population and Migrants are much less in Chennai. From table 4 it also comes out that percentage increase in male migrants in the metro cities are more than double except in Chennai. This is alarming for the metro cities which are becoming overburdened with the problems of housing and provisioning of basic civic amenities.

Table 6: Reasons for male migration in metropolitan cities in 2001

City	Work	Business	Education	Marriage
Kolkata	17.75	2.28	1.16	0.30
Mumbai	34.52	0.87	1.19	0.21
Chennai	18.71	1.29	1.26	0.67
Delhi Delhi	32.04	0.64	1.10	0.15

Source: Census of India

The main reason for migration in all the metro cities was found to be for work followed by business and education. Marriage is the least reason for migration for males in four metro cities. This is shown in table 6. Mumbai hosted the largest percent of migrants in 2001 followed by Delhi, Kolkata and Chennai. For business Kolkata is ahead of other states and majority went to Chennai for education. Male migration for marriage is less than 1% in all the metro cities.

Urbanization and Migration

Table7: Annual growth rate of population of four metro cities

City	1981	1991	2001
Mumbai	49.3	41.3	29.9
Kolkata	23.9	19.9	19.9
Delhi	53	51.5	37.7
Chennai	40.3	26.4	18.5

Source: Census of India

In India a close relation is found between urbanization and economic development (Sovani 1964, Bhagat 2012). About 65% of Gross Domestic product accrue from urban areas that comprise of one third of India's total population (31% urban , 2011 census).India has about 8000 cities and towns, 53 million plus cities , consisting 43% of India's urban population (Bhagbat and Mohanty 2009) Bhagbat (2009). India has experienced rapid urban population growth .Net rural to urban classification (preceding the census 2011) contributed about one third to urban population compared to one fourth by net rural to urban migration(Bhagat 2012). Therefore pattern of urbanization in India is a complex process of changes in the characteristics of human settlements. It is not simply a rural to urban transfer of labour and population. Urban areas have better access to civic facilities which attract migrants from other areas. With that there are huge problems like proliferation of slums, overcrowding, pollution, urban crime and violence etc. According to estimate of United Nations, India has low level of urbanization. The projected urban population of India is 814 million ie 50% of total population by 2050(UN 2015).

Migration and urbanization in India have historically been linked to stagnation of agriculture and lack of sectoral diversification within agrarian economy. The growth rates of agricultural production and income has been noted to be low and unstable over the past several decades. This resulted lack of livelihood opportunities in rural areas. A low rate of infrastructural investment in rural areas also affected agriculture adversely. This has led to migration from several backward rural areas.

In India regional inequality is associated with the process of urbanization and migration.Migration has huge potential to improve human development. Migration also helps to reduce poverty. In India, rural to urban migration consists of migrants from relatively better off sections of population and also very poor people searching employment in urban areas. People from better off section migrate for better education and better job opportunities. Poor people migrate for economic improvement and reduction of poverty.

The two main outcomes of rural to urban migration are efficiency of land use and poverty reduction. Seasonal and temporary migration from rural to urban areas is also a common feature of migration in India. It not only helps to reduce poverty but creates a positive impact on building assets and improving education and health care facilities. However migration is not seen positively in India, because of lack of integration of migration with process of development. Integration of migration and urbanization is needed with development policies

Urbanisation is the rate of increase in urban population. In table 6 we find in four metro cities rate of growth of urban population have declined from 1981 to 2001. This may be due to declassification of urban area or increased out migration from these cities.

The correlation coefficients between urbanization and migration of four metro cities for the years 1991 and 2001 are found to be - 0.05 and 0.34 respectively. It shows a poor relationship between the two variables.

Migration and urbanization must be taken into consideration in the context of emergence of global cities. These cities are not only linked with national market but with international market. The strategy of economic reform and globalization are leading to growth

of industries and business creating employment opportunities in global cities. Given this perspective, policies should be framed in such a way to harness the potential of migration in cities for promoting a balanced settlement structure.

Census 2011

In the census 2011, Uttar Pradesh and Bihar are found to have disproportionately high number of out migrants. In 2011, 20.9 million people migrated outside the state from Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. Hindi belt is the main source of migrants. Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh accounted for 50% of total interstate migrants.

Table 8: Per capita Growth Rates of Net State Domestic Product during 1993-2009

State	1993-2001	2001-2009
Bihar	1.41	5.86
Maharashtra	2.38	8.13
Uttar Pradesh	1.31	3.88
West Bengal	5.04	5
Tamil Nadu	3.99	6.75
Madhya Pradesh	2.13	3.37
India	3.34	5.85

Source: Kumar Subramaniam, 2011

From table 8 we find the per capita growth rates of Net State Domestic Product of Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh are quite less than national average. This can be a possible reason for increasing number of migrants from these states to relatively developed states like Maharashtra, Tamilnadu etc.

Migrants constitute more than one third of population in metros like Delhi and Mumbai. Maharashtra, Delhi, Gujarat, Uttar Pradesh, Haryana housed 50% of country's interstate migrants.

The number of interstate migrants grew at 55% between 1991 and 2001. This came down to 33% between 2001 and 2011.

Conclusion

Average percentage of migrants in total population is 28.9% from 1961 to 2001. In 1991 and 2001, marriage was the main reason for migration which is high for females. Among males the main reason for migration is work or employment.

In 2001 census, Maharashtra housed largest number of migrants followed by Delhi and West Bengal.

In 1991 and 2001, percentage of males in total migrants were more than fifty percent in the four metro cities; Mumbai Delhi, Kolkata and Chennai. In 1991 and 2001 the total and male migrants both increased in four metro cities except in Chennai.

Taking into account the percentage increase in population and percentage increase in male migration it comes out that in both the cases Delhi is at the top position followed by Mumbai, Kolkata and Chennai.

The main reason for migration in all the metro cities was work followed by business and education. Mumbai had the largest number of migrants for work followed by Delhi, Kolkata and Chennai.

For business Kolkata is ahead of other metro cities and majority went to Chennai for education. Male migration for marriage is less than one percent in the metro cities.

In India, regional economic inequality is associated with process of urbanization and migration.

Migrants from better off sections migrate for better job opportunities and for better higher education. Whereas migration of poor migrants take place to improve economic condition and reduction of poverty.

However, migration is not seen positively in India because of lack of integration between urbanization and migration. Low values of correlation coefficients also reflect that.

According to 2011 census, Uttar Pradesh and Bihar have large number of out migrants which amounted to 20.9 million in 2011.

Migrants constitute more than one third of population in metros like Delhi and Mumbai.

The number of interstate migrants grew at 55% between 1991 and 2001. This came to 33% between 2001 and 2011.

References

Banerjee Biswajit 1986 Rural to Urban Migration and the urban Labour Market, A case Study of Delhi, Bombay and New Delhi, Himalaya Publishing House

Bhagat R B and Mohanty Soumaya 2009 Emerging Pattern of urbanization and the Contribution of Migration in Urban Growth in India, Asian Population studies Vol5, No.1

Bhagat R B 2010 Internal Migration in India; are the underprivileged migrating more, Asia Pacific Population journal Vol 25 No 1 2010

Directorate of Census Operation, 1991, 2001 2011, Census of India, Migration tables, New Delhi

Harris J R and Todaro M P 1970 Migration Unemployment and Development, A Two Sector Analysis, The American Economic Review Vol LX No. 1

Kumar U 2013 India's Demographic Transition: Boon or Bane? Asia and the Pacific Policy Studies 1

Kumar U and Subramaniam A 2011 Indias Frowth in the 2000s : Four Facts Peterson Institute for International Economics

Kundu A 2007 Migration and Urbanization in India in the Context of Poverty Alleviation, Paper Beijing China

Kundu A 2011 Politics and Economics of Urban Growth, Economic and Political Weekly 46(20) pp 10-12

Sinha S k 1986 Internal Migration in India 1961-81 New Delhi Office of the Registrar General Ministry of Home Affairs

